

Neutron Stars and the EOS of Dense Matter II: Neutron Star Universal Love

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Summary

Our history and knowledge of both neutron stars and the nucleus has progressed incrementally over the past 90 years since the original work of Oppenheimer and others. The main recent change has been the discovery that neutron stars can be fairly massive (about two solar masses) with a radius of around ten km. The effect of most changes to the EOS - such as moderately changing the stiffness or limiting the sound speed squared - is within the ten percent uncertainty of the data. For example, the maximum mass $m=M=m_1$ which peaks as a function of the scaled radius r/r_{SW} does not vary beyond these limits. The effect of limiting the speed of sound squared in neutron matter to $.5 c^2$ is to reduce the mass (2.2 to 1.9 solar masses for $K=274$ or 1.9 to 1.8 for $K=202$) or change the radius of the neutron star by less than ten percent. A symmetry in several quantities cross models or EOSs was identified in my first paper. A peak or hook in both the mass curve and the binding energy curve was also identified; this limits the maximum mass

of a neutron star as a domain of instability is approached. Rotating stars offer potentially new insight into both stiffness and other high density features of the EOS. The moment of inertia and associated values such as Love numbers are readily calculated here for several models. The scaled moment of inertia I/mr^2 is a good indicator of the EOS or model correspondence with current or future high precision data. The universal Love number relation is also of value. This and other rotating star measurements can be used to rule out (or in) a softer EOS or any softening due to phase transitions or structure in the speed of sound. Comparing data and theory for different mass neutron stars (e.g. 1.4 solar mass vs. 2.0 solar mass) is a particularly sensitive measure. I have here identified simple equations that give the vibrational frequency cross several models as well as a universal Love number relationship. Further the two main approaches to different types of vibrations have relationships such as crossing points. At low beta (high lambda) the Fermi pressure dominates whereas at high beta (low lambda) the relativistic sound speed squared cutoff dominates. In between at intermediate beta, lambda values the symmetry energy makes a difference so that future experimental and theoretical work in this regard will be of interest. Most of the models agree fairly well with existing data.

Introduction

This work follows up a previous study of neutron stars [1]. Over the past 40 years [2] there has been some limited progress [3] in the understanding of the equation of state (EOS) of ultra-dense matter. The seminal work was done long ago by Tolman [4] and Oppenheimer [5] and appears in most textbooks [6]. Nevertheless, a variety of models [7] continue to proliferate some with exotic features such as with cores of strange matter, quark matter, or dark matter. Some have even proposed changes to general relativity itself because of both the need to connect more fundamentally with quantum physics and due to new cosmology data. It appears from our investigations that relatively simple models [8] are able to account for current data and also a few high precision measurements [9] of neutron star observables may be used to rule out or in softer or more exotic EOS.

I have here identified simple equations that give the vibrational frequency cross several models as well as a universal Love number relationship. Further the two main approaches to different types of vibrations have relationships such as crossing points.

Our Investigation

We have undertaken a relatively straightforward investigation using the TOV equation

- $dp/dr = -G m \rho / r^2 (1 + 4 \pi p r^3 / m c^2) (1 + p / \rho c^2) / (1 - 2 GM / r c^2)$

and a few simple models which are solved analytically (where possible) or numerically when necessary [10].

Some of the basic internal variables of the neutron star cross several models are shown in Figures 1-6. This includes pressure, density, $dp/d\rho$, dp/dr , γ_{mac} , and others.

Further, we have solved the slowly rotating neutron star coupled equations [11]

- $dj/dr = 8 \pi / 3 \rho r^4 (1 + p / \rho c^2) w / \exp(\nu + \lambda)$
- $dw/dr = G \exp(\nu + \lambda) j / (c^2 r^4)$

for the moment of inertia $I = j(R)/W$ with $W = w + 2GJ/c^2 R^3$ at $r=R$. This extends the simple classical moment of inertia to account for basic general relativity.

Also we have solved the Riccati equation [12]

- $r dy/dr + y^2 + y F(r) + r^2 G(r) = 0$

for the variable y at $r=R$ which allows the determination of the second Love number [13,14]

- $k_2 = \frac{8}{5} \beta^5 (1 - 2\beta)^2 [2 + 2\beta(y - 1) - y] / [2\beta \{6 - 3y + 3\beta(5y - 8)\} + 4\beta^3 \{13 - 11y + \beta(3y - 2) + 2\beta^2(1 + y)\} + 3(1 - 2\beta)^2 \{2 - y + 2\beta(y - 1)\} \text{Ln}(1 - 2\beta)]$.

Note that the equation for k_2 appears in error in print in one paper, though there is an erratum correction [13] and the second paper gives the correct result in agreement with the erratum

[13,14]. The functions $F(r)$ and $G(r)$ are defined in the literature [14]. The tidal deformability is defined in terms of the Love [16] number as

- $\lambda = \frac{2}{3} k_2 / \beta^5$

and this allows the presentation of a universality relation. The universality relation plots a scaled moment of inertia

- $I_{\text{scaled}} = I_{\text{love}} = I / m^3 / (G/c^2)^2$

to get the so-called I Love Q type plots.

Tabular Data Results

Table 1 gives select results for the main two EOS and reference models. ρ_C is in units of 10^{15} g/cc; r is in km; m is in solar masses; I is in $\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^2$. $\beta = .057$ (smaller for pf only case) and $\rho_{\text{MEc}} = .291$ so ρ_{bc} is about $\rho_{\text{NM}} = .283$. Note that all of the I_{love} numbers for the same beta value are the same cross models in this case. The tidal deformability is significantly smaller in the two realistic nuclear models (202 and 274) and significantly greater for the pf only (Oppenheimer) case.

Table 2 gives select results for the main two EOS and reference models. ρ_C is in units of 10^{15} g/cc; r is in km; m is in solar masses; I is in $\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^2$. As discussed in our first paper, the r/r_{sw} values here are mostly around 2 which is near optimal for high mass neutron stars.

Table 3 gives select results for the main two EOS and reference models. ρ_C is in units of 10^{15} g/cc; r is in km; m is in solar masses; I is in $\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^2$. Two (mass) sizes of neutron stars are shown: the biggest around 1.8-2.0 solar masses and a smaller mass star about 1.3-1.5 solar masses. The beta values are about .235 for the more massive (smaller) star and .176 for the less massive (bigger) star for NUC274 and .221 (.165) for NUC 202. The tidal deformability (not

shown) is a rapidly decreasing function of the beta values being very large (thousands or millions) for low beta and very small (1-100) for high beta or high mass (for the same radius) neutron stars.

Vibrations

For calculating frequencies of vibration, we consider two approaches, that due to Bardeen and Chandrasekhar (radial) which defines quantities P,Q,W in terms of the density and pressure profile of the star and related quantities PLMI,QLMI,WLMI due to Lindblom, Mendell, Ipser and others (non-radial). Mostly we shall focus on the LMI frequencies since they are of interest in the tidal deformation process that leads to gravitational waves that have now been observed.

The typical equation for vibration is

- $u'' + P'/P u' + (Q/P + W/P \omega^2/c^2) u = 0$

where $\text{bdamp} = P'/P$ is a damping factor and $\text{sig}^2 = (Q/P + W/P \omega^2/c^2)$ is a driving factor.

This type of equation appears in many parts of physics and materials science (see for example Kolsky page 66 [16]). The function u is different in Bardeen and LMI approaches due to initial and boundary (surface) conditions. The frequencies are found by the usual minimization variational method (see Morse and Feshbach ref. [15]). Frequencies and frequency ratios are shown in Figures 14-16. The ratios come from dividing by a base frequency which for a given neutron star model is

- $\text{nubase} = \text{Sqrt}[G M/R^3] / 2 \text{ Pi} .$

Some observations:

1. W/P is the same in both Bardeen and LMI
2. W/Q is the same order of magnitude and LMI and Bardeen have a crossing point

3. Q/P LMI and Bardeen have a crossing point
4. PLMI follows a beta distribution
5. QLMI follows roughly a Fermi type distribution
6. $\text{sigBardeen} = -\text{sig}2\text{LMI} = Q/P + W/P \text{ om}^2/c^2$ at a crossing point.

Examples of the crossings are shown in Figure 7.

Approximate Formulae

Both numerically and by expansion of the appropriate equations it is found that over a wide range of beta values (0 to .35), the LMI frequencies may be approximated by a formula

- $\text{nuLMI} = f c \text{ Sqrt}[-\text{QLMI}/\text{WLMI}] / 2 \text{ Pi Sqrt}[1-2 \text{ bet}]$

where f is a factor that depends on the model and QLMI is the minimum QLMI value and WLMI is the maximum WLMI value. Typical values are .97 for our nuclear EOS and .88 for Tolman 7.

Furthermore, it is also found that the LMI frequencies may be represented by a second formula

- $\text{nuLMI} = g / 2 \text{ Pi Sqrt}[\text{dp}/\text{drho}] (1 - 2 \text{ bet})^{(3/2)} / R$

where R is the neutron star radius and g is a numerical factor. Typical values for F are 5 for our nuclear EOS and 2.6 for Tolman 7. Lamb, Love [16], and others long ago (1879) related the frequency to the fluid dynamic speed.

Equating the two previous equations leads to the following result

- $-\text{Qmin}/\text{Wmax} = F \text{ dp}/\text{drho} / c^2 (1 - 2 \text{ bet})^4 / R^2 .$

Thus from the first equation we have that

- $\text{nuLMI} = f c \text{ Sqrt}[F \text{ dp}/\text{drho} / c^2 (1 - 2 \text{ bet})^4 / R^2] / 2 \text{ Pi Sqrt}[1-2 \text{ bet}]$ or

- $\text{nuLMI} = f c \text{ Sqrt}[F \text{ dp}/\text{drho} / c^2] (1 - 2 \text{ bet})^{(3/2)} / (2 \text{ Pi R}) .$

This last equation has a very simple physical meaning in that for any wave $c = \nu \lambda$; thus an associated wavelength is different for the vibration in the neutron star medium. Obviously the factors in the last equation can be combined so that $f \sqrt{F}$ is for example 2.17 for our nuclear EOS and 1.42 for Tolman 7.

Figures

Some of the basic internal variables of the neutron star cross several models are shown in Figures 1-6.

Extracted variables such as mass, radius, binding energies, and moments of inertia are shown in Figures 7-13. Figure 12 abcde show PLMI, QLMI, and various ratios.

Frequencies and frequency ratios are shown in Figures 14-16.

Figure 17 shows the relationship of Q_{\min} and W_{\max} cross models.

Figure 18 gives the extracted wavelength for the vibrations scaled by the star radius.

Figure 19 shows how the tidal deformability relates to the beta factor cross models.

Figure 20 gives the universal Love relationship.

Finally, in Figure 21 we show the Love relationship compared to the first four terms of the Chan [14] formula (here in Mathematica code)

- $I_{\text{love}}[x_] :=$

$$\frac{2}{5} (2x)^{2/5} \left(1 + \frac{22}{7} (1/(2x))^{1/5} + \frac{8726}{2205} (1/(2x))^{3/5} + \frac{79840}{33957} (1/(2x))^{5/5} \right)$$

where $x = \lambda$ is the (scaled) tidal deformability and I_{love} is the scaled relativistic moment of inertia. The agreement is fairly good cross the reference models. The difference with our simple nuclear models NUC202 and NUC274 at intermediate tidal deformability is perhaps due to the effect of the symmetry energy. At low beta (high λ) the Fermi pressure dominates

whereas at high beta (low lambda) the relativistic sound speed squared cutoff dominates. In between at intermediate beta, lambda values the symmetry energy makes a difference so that future experimental and theoretical work in this regard will be of interest.

Figure 22 focuses on the area of interest for neutron stars as found in nature. Most of the models can explain the single data point (the LIGO/Virgo result that tidal deformability lambda is about 1000) that exists. Notice that the Chan expansion is NOT model independent (so NOT universal). This is probably because of the assumption made by Chan that the density exists as a Taylor series in the pressure. Clearly this is NOT always the case since for example they can be related via a power law such as in the Tooper model. The derivatives of such a power law do not all exist at $p=0$. Future experimental data will tighten the single data point to hopefully several high precision points.

Tables

Table 1. Select results for the main two EOS and reference models. ρ_c is in units of 10^{15} g/cc; r is in km; m is in solar masses; I is in $\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^2$. $\beta=0.057$ (smaller for pf only case) and $\rho_{\text{MEc}}=0.291$ so ρ_{bc} about $\rho_{\text{NM}}=0.283$. Note that all of the love numbers for the same beta value are the same cross models in this case. The tidal deformability is significantly smaller in the two realistic nuclear models (202 and 274) and significantly greater for the pf only (Oppenheimer) case.

EOS	r	m	dim1	$I/10^{45}$	freq .LM I	freq. Bardeen	Ratio LMI	-Q LMI	Tidal def.	dim1 first mom.	llove
NUC 202	11.4	0.439	0.0408	0.367	2150	1945	2.16	4.83	113 k	0.67	100
NUC 274	10.9	0.418	0.0401	0.327	2329	2206	2.23	4.85	108 k	0.66	103
Tolman 7	12.5	0.483	0.0438	0.432	1435	1880	1.56	4.76	250 k	0.714	88
Tooper	10.8	0.424	0.0414	0.321	1525	2519	1.44	4.83	282 k	0.67	97
Buch- dahl	13.3	0.514	0.0450	0.496	1338	1658	1.57	4.71	216 k	0.70	84
Nariai	12.7	0.489	0.0460	0.471	1421	1806	1.58	4.73	276 j	0.72	93
pf only	16.8	0.452	0.0367	0.511	1046	776	1.85	4.89	677 k	0.87	127

Table 2. Select results for the main two EOS and reference models. ρ_C is in units of 10^{15} g/cc; r is in km; m is in solar masses; I is in $\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^2$. As discussed in our first paper, the r/r_{sw} values here are mostly around 2 which is near optimal for high mass neutron stars.

EOS	ρ_C	r	m	r_{sw}	r_{sn}	I/mr^2	$I/10^{45}$	k_2	Tidal deform	λ_{love}
NUC274	1.48	11.4	1.84	2.10	2.41	0.356	1.70	0.0436	38	6.3
NUC202	1.88	11.3	1.82	2.10	2.66	0.310	1.43	0.0339	29	5.5
Tolman 7	1.55	10.9	1.70	2.17	1.88	0.319	1.27	0.0451	47	5.9
Sly	2.63	10.1	2.04	1.67	4.12	0.367	1.51	0.0194	5.3	4.1
Max. Uni.	1.55	8.19	1.79	1.55	1.55	.40/.45	.95/1.1	0.0106	2.0	4.3
Tooper	1.88	8.65	1.37	2.14	1.32	0.706	0.71	0.0663	63	6.3
pf	1.90	11.1	0.69	5.47	1.59	0.193	0.32	0.0556	5805	13

Table 3. Select results for the main two EOS and reference models. ρ_C is in units of 10^{15} g/cc; r is in km; m is in solar masses; I is in $\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^2$. Two (mass) sizes of neutron stars are shown: the biggest around 1.8-2.0 solar masses and a smaller mass star about 1.3-1.5 solar masses. The beta values are about .235 for the more massive (smaller) star and .176 for the less massive (bigger) star for NUC274 and .221 (.165) for NUC 202. The tidal deformability (not shown) is a rapidly decreasing function of the beta values being very large (thousands or millions) for low beta and very small (1-100) for high beta or high mass (for the same radius) neutron stars.

EOS	ρ_C	r	m	rr_{sw}	rr_{sn}	I/mr^2	$I/10^{45}$	k_2	I_{love}
NUC274	1.32	12.1	1.93	2.12	2.15	0.333	1.87	0.0436	1.07
NUC274	0.77	12.6	1.50	2.85	0.91	0.317	1.52	0.0731	2.16
ratio		0.96	1.29				1.23	0.60	2.0
NUC202	1.57	11.9	1.78	2.27	2.27	0.293	1.48	0.0383	1.20
NUC202	0.88	12.3	1.38	3.02	0.97	0.302	1.26	0.0736	2.65
ratio		0.97	1.29				1.18	0.52	2.2

Conclusions

The effect of most changes to the EOS - such as moderately changing the stiffness or limiting the sound speed - is within the ten percent uncertainty of the data. For example, the maximum mass $m=M=m_1$ which peaks as a function of the scaled radius r/r_{SW} does not vary beyond these limits. The effect of limiting the speed of sound squared in neutron matter to $.5 c^2$ is to reduce the mass (2.2 to 1.9 solar masses for $K=274$ or 1.9 to 1.8 for $K=202$) or change the radius of the neutron star by less than ten percent. Thus it is unlikely that much more can be learned without more better high precision data from neutron stars and nuclear experiments. The recent NICER data indicates the beginning of this era. A symmetry in several quantities cross models or EOSs was identified in my first paper on this subject. A peak or hook in both the mass curve and the binding energy curve was also identified; this limits the maximum mass of a neutron star as a domain of instability is approached. I have here identified simple equations that give the vibrational frequency cross several models as well as a universal Love number relationship. Further the two main approaches to different types of vibrations have relationships such as crossing points. At low beta (high lambda) the Fermi pressure dominates whereas at high beta (low lambda) the relativistic sound speed squared cutoff dominates. In between at intermediate beta, lambda values the symmetry energy makes a difference so that future experimental and theoretical work in this regard will be of interest. Most of the models agree fairly well with existing data.

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Figures

Figure 1. Density. $\beta=0.148$ and $\rho_{MEC}=0.761$ are used.

Figure 2. Pressure.

Figure 3. $dp/drho$

Figure 4. dp/dr .

Figure 5. Gammac.

Figure 7a. Example of crossing points.

Figure 7b. The damping term in the vibrational differential equation.

Figure 7c. Example of crossing points.

Figure 7d. Example of crossing points.

Figure 6a. Γ_{mac} for $\beta=0.061$ $\rho_{\text{bc}}=3 \times 10^{14}$ g/cc case.

Figure 6b. Γ_{mac}'

Figure 6b. Γ_{mac}' (alternate figure)

Figure 6c. $\Gamma_{\text{mac}}'/\Gamma_{\text{mac}}$.

Figure 6c. $\Gamma_{\text{mac}}'/\Gamma_{\text{mac}}$ alternate figure.

Figure 8. $1/h dp/dr$ where $h = p + \rho c^2$; this function serves a similar purpose as Γ'/Γ . For the Tooper model, the slope of this curve at low r values is $-4/3 \pi G \rho c (1 + 3/2 \beta)/c^2$ which is also equal to $\gamma/(\gamma-1)$ times the slope of the Γ'/Γ curve. We use the Tooper case $\gamma=3$ corresponding to $n=1/2$ in the Tooper equations. The other various models studied here have central gamma values in the range 2.37-2.72.

Figure 9. Neutron star mass. The mass has a near linear dependence on beta over a wide range.

Figure 10. Neutron star radius. The mass is nearly constant over a wide range except in the old classic (Oppie) pf only model.

Figure 11a. Gravitational binding energy per unit mass $\text{dim}1 = d1m/m = (m_4 - m_1)/m_1$. The BE may be represented by $\text{bet} + b \text{bet}^2 + c \text{bet}^3$ where a, b, c are constants in the mass moment expansion. For simple models such as Maximum Uniform and Tolman 7, these constants are given by integer ratios for example $3/5$ or $5/7$.

Figure 11b. Tooper binding energy $d2m = (m3-m1)$. Since $d1m/m1 = a \text{ bet} + b \text{ bet}^2 + c \text{ bet}^3 = (m4-m1)/m1$ and equation may also be found for $d2m$.

Figure 12 a. PLMI.

Figure 12 b. QLMI.

Figure 12 c. QLMI pf only.

Figure 12 d. W/P Bardeen which equals W/P LMI.

Figure 12e. W over Q Bardeen

Figure 12f. Q over P Bardeen

Figure 13. Moment of inertia vs. tidal deformability.

Figure 14. LMI frequencies.

Figure 15. Ratio of LMI frequencies to base frequency.

Figure 16. Bardeen and other frequencies are shown for reference.

Figure 17. Qmin and Wmax relationship. Note that in certain cases W rises very rapidly near the surface. In this case by Wmax we mean the value before the rapid rise; alternatively one can look at Wmax values at the radial point where Pmax occurs.

Figure 18. The wavelength λ defined by $c = \nu \lambda$ where c is the wave speed and ν is the LMI frequency.

Figure 19. Tidal deformability versus the beta factor.

The tidal deformability (not shown) is a rapidly decreasing function of the beta values being very large (thousands or millions) for low beta and very small (1-100) for high beta or high mass (for the same radius) neutron stars.

Figure 20. The so-called universal love relations figure. For most EOS, the curve is very similar. For a maximum uniform and our realistic nuclear EOS the curve is somewhat higher than in the other models at intermediate tidal deformability.

Figure 21. The universal love relations figure compared to the Chan expansion.

Figure 22. The universal love relations figure compared to the Chan expansion in the region of experimental interest. Like the $ga=9$ Tooper case, the maximal uniform model will also exceed the Chan expansion most everywhere.

